

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND ELEMENTAL PROFILES OF SMOKE-DRIED FISH SPECIES SOLD IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the physico-chemical properties and mineral elements profile of four common smoke-dried fish species in open markets in Imo State, Nigeria. The fish species were *Gymnarchus niloticus* (Trunkfish), *Rita sacertodum* (Thailand), *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish) and *Ethmalosa fimbriata* (Bonga fish). Each of the fish species was analysed for their physico-chemical attributes and mineral profiles to ascertain their quality and safety. Basic physico-chemical attributes investigated include peroxide value (PV), total volatile basic nitrogen (TVBN) and pH. The PV values ranged from $4.62 \pm 0.03 - 32.97 \pm 0.05$ mEq O₂/kg in *G. niloticus*, $2.79 \pm 0.01 - 34.83 \pm 0.05$ mEq O₂/kg in *R. sacertodum*, $0.8 \pm 0.01 - 8.82 \pm 0.02$ mEq O₂/kg in *C. gariepinus* and $6.06 \pm 0.06 - 18.78 \pm 0.11$ mEq O₂/kg in *E. fimbriata*. The TVB-N values were within acceptable limits, from $7.29 \pm 0.1 - 10.36 \pm 0.1$ mg/kg, $7.81 \pm 0.1 - 10.15 \pm 0.1$ mg/kg, $5.75 \pm 0.18 - 10.40 \pm 0.25$ mg/kg and $7.44 \pm 0.1 - 10.56 \pm 0.2$ mg/kg for *G. niloticus*, *R. sacertodum*, *C. gariepinus* and *E. fimbriata*, respectively. pH values were above 7 except *R. sacertodum* (6.97) and *E. fimbriata* (6.92) found in the open market of Anara. The highest pH value was 7.99 in *C. gariepinus*. The fish species contained elements reflecting the mineral composition of the water bodies they were harvested, and possibly contaminants from poor handling. Trace elements such as iron (Fe), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), and chromium (Cr) were detected at varying concentrations. Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, and Cr exceeded recommended limits in some locations; this may be a potential health risk. Arsenic (As) and lead (Pb), known for their toxicity, were not detected across all sample locations.

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INTRODUCTION

Health, nutrition, and convenience are key drivers of the global food industry today. Fish stands out as one of the healthiest foods due to its rich nutrient profile. It offers high-quality protein and healthful polyunsaturated fatty acids that are essential to human diets (Mohan *et al.*, 2018). It also serves as a staple in the diet and a good source of elemental micronutrients and, in some cases, heavy metals. Due to its high fat and protein content, fish is highly susceptible to spoilage, resulting from both intrinsic and extrinsic factors. The chemical breakdown of the protein and fat contents leads to speedy deteriorative changes in fish quality, which subsequently compromise the safety and nutritional quality of the fish (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2013 and Adaka *et al.*, 2017). Assessing the quality and safety of fish by the visual appearance or freshness is not feasible due to the complexity of quality deterioration in fish flesh. Thus, evaluating physicochemical properties and elemental profiles is crucial for ascertaining fish safety and potential health implications for human consumption. Such information highlights the deteriorative changes in fish and the required conditions to maximize and retain the fish quality. Identifying the possible risks in the consumption of smoke-dried fish is important and ensure that the permitted limits are not exceeded. Certain quality indices can be used to quantify the level of fish quality retention or deterioration, and these include total volatile

basic nitrogen (TVBN), peroxide value, pH and elemental analysis (Adeyeye *et al.*, 2016).

In smoke-dried fish, poor handling and storage are very crucial to the safe keeping of the product and can cause lipid rancidity, which can lead to unpleasant flavours, harmful hydroperoxide compounds, and free radicals (Rasul *et al.*, 2020). The smoked fish exposed in an open market for retailing under the intense heat of the sun and other environmental conditions causes a gradual loss of freshness and quality. Numerous unsaturated lipids in fish oil contribute to the creation of distinctive flavours and the generation of free radicals at the onset of rancidity. The presence of high concentrations of hydroperoxide and these radicals in food is a sign of poor quality. Oxidation of hydroperoxide results in increased peroxide levels and development of off-flavour in fish products during drying, handling and storage under poor handling conditions, and this lowers the value of the product. The hydroperoxides, which are the primary products of lipid oxidation, reduce the protein digestibility of fish; the secondary oxidation products can harm membranes and cause ageing, cardiovascular disease, atherosclerosis, and growth tumours (Rasul *et al.*, 2020). According to Jeyakumari *et al.* (2018), hydroperoxide can be detected by exploiting its oxidation potential, and the concentration can be quantified through either titrimetric or spectrophotometric methods. The most widely used method, however, relies on iodometric titration. The peroxide value (PV) is a valuable indicator for evaluating the quality of fat, and a value exceeding 10mg/kg is indicative

of a reduction in fish quality (Hidayah *et al.*, 2022).

Total Volatile Bases Nitrogen (TVB-N) is a broad term that refers to the measurement of numerous nitrogenous compounds such as trimethylamine (TMA), dimethylamine (DMA), ammonia, and other volatile basic nitrogen-containing substances associated with seafood deterioration (Elshehawy *et al.*, 2016; Jeyakumari *et al.*, 2018). It largely represents protein breakdown within a sample, which can be attributed to bacterial activities (Idakwo *et al.*, 2016; Jeyakumari *et al.*, 2018). TVB-N is mostly composed of ammonia as well as primary, secondary, and tertiary amines, the by-products of the breakdown of protein in the fish muscle by bacteria. The TVB-N value is an important indicator used to assess the freshness and quality of fish (Alkuraieef *et al.*, 2020) and is frequently used together with TMA measurement (Jeyakumari *et al.*, 2018). Typically, a TVB-N level of 35-40 mg per 100g of fish muscle is considered acceptable; above this value, the fish is considered spoiled (Nowsad *et al.*, 2021). The TVBN value is a useful tool for determining the freshness of the fish. Value above the limit renders the dried fish a health risk and unsafe for human consumption. Another reliable indicator of the degree of freshness or spoilage of fish is the pH. The breakdown of the protein by proteolytic microorganisms increases the pH, promoting the growth of the pH-sensitive spoilage bacterium, *Shewanella putrefaciens* (Ikutegbe and Sikoki, 2014). The increase in the volatile bases from the breakdown of nitrogenous compounds by endogenous or microbial enzymes may also

result in the rise of the pH. (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2013). Most fish have a high tendency to accumulate elemental components in their bodies. Some of which are essential to human health (iron (Fe), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and selenium (Se)), some may be non-essential and non-toxic while others such as chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg) and lead (Pb) are generally known to be toxic and known for their negative side effects on humans (Tako, 2022) when the permitted level is exceeded (Maulu *et al.*, 2021).

Fresh and processed fish contain a certain level of contaminants depending on the source and processing method, and of interest in this project is the smoke-dried fish, highly consumed by the people of the Eastern states of Nigeria. Different studies have elucidated the health challenges associated with different modes of processing, and there is detailed information on the contaminants acquired from the source and during the processing. The common practice is to keep the smoke-dried fish for as long as it takes to sell, while the freshly smoked can be mixed with the old. Most of the retailers are not educated, and the extent of contamination or deterioration in the quality of the dried fish has never been considered important. This project seeks to elucidate the extent of deterioration in smoke-dried fish from the retail point, the handling practices of different retailers of commonly consumed smoke-fried fish in Imo State of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

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Smoke-dried *Gymnarchus niloticus* (Trunkfish), *Rita sacertodum* (Thailand), *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish) and *Ethmalosa fimbriata* (Bonga fish) were purchased from 9 open markets in Imo State. Three markets were selected from each of the three senatorial zones in the State (Fig1): Imo-East (IE), Imo-West (IW) and Imo-North (IN) (Table 1). From the Imo-East (IE) zone were selected; the Relief market in Owerri (coded IEA), Afor-Ogbe market in Mbaize (IEB), Irete market in Irete (IEC). From Imo-West (IW) zone, Daily market in Orlu (IWD), Afor-Umuaka market in Umuaka (IWE), Orie-Akokwa market in Akokwa (IWF); and from Imo-North zone, Obowo market in Obowo (IMG), Anara market in Mbano (INH), Orie-Amaraku in Amaraku (INI). (Table 1). Each species was purchased from 10 different retail points from

each of the 9 open markets and blended to represent the species sample. A total of 36 samples were used for this study.

Sample preparation

Smoked fish samples were purchased from the ten different retailers in the open markets. They were kept in polythene bags and transported straight to the laboratory. Each sample was carefully de-skinned, de-gutted and de-boned. The dried edible portions were separated and milled to a fine particle size. The ten samples of a particular fish species were blended to represent the sample of the fish species from the specific market location and coded as given in the table. The 36 samples were kept differently in air-tight bags and stored at 4 °C prior to the physicochemical and elemental analysis.

Fig. 1 Map of Nigeria showing Imo State and the three senatorial zones

Source: Researchgate.net

Table 1. Codes for the sample Market location

Zone	Sample code	Market name
Imo-East (IE)	IEA	Relief market, Owerri
	IEB	Afor Ogbe market, Mbaise
	IEC	Irete market, Irete
Imo-West (IW)	IWD	Daily market, Orlu
	IWE	Afor Umuaka market, Umuaka
	IWF	Orie Akokwa market, Akokwa
Imo-North (IN)	ING	Obowo market, Obowo
	INH	Anara market, Mbano
	INI	Orie Amaraku, market, Amaraku

Peroxide Value (PV) Determination

The lipid extract was obtained from the fish samples using the Soxhlet method for oil extraction. About 1 g of the extracted oil samples were weighed into 250 ml of chloroform, containing 0.01% butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), and shaken for 30 secs to dissolve the lipid. A 50 ml of solvent mixture (glacial/acetic acid: chloroform 3:2 v/v) was then added, and the flask was gently rotated to facilitate mixing and kept in a dark cupboard for 3 mins. Distilled water (100 ml) was added to the mixture, and the liberated iodine was titrated against 0.05M sodium thiosulphate solution using 2% freshly prepared starch as an indicator. The peroxide value was determined as given below (Adeyemi *et al.* 2013).

Calculation:

$$\text{mEq} \frac{O_2}{k_9} = \frac{m(v_1 - v_0) \times MNa_2S_2O \times 2 \times 1000}{m} \quad (1)$$

Where:

V₁ = Titre value of 0.05M Na₂S₂O of the sample,

V₀ = Titre value 0.05M Na₂S₂O of the blank titration

M Na₂S₂O = Molarity of Na₂S₂O = 0,05

M = Mass of the lipid sample (g)

Total Volatile Basic Nitrogen (TVBN) Determination

The total volatile basic nitrogen (TVBN) was determined according to the method described by the Commission of the European Communities (2005). About 10 g ± 0.1g of the ground sample was weighed; this was mixed with 6 % of 90 ml perchloric acid solution, homogenized for 2 mins and then filtered. Fifty millilitres of the filtrate was alkalized using 20

% (6.5 ml) NaOH, and drops of phenolphthalein indicator and a few drops of antifoaming agent were added. The mixture was steam distilled. The distillation was regulated to collect 100 ml of the distillate within 10 mins. The steam distillation was regulated so that about 100 ml of distillate was produced within 10 mins of 100 ml 3 % boric acid. The distillate in boric acid was titrated against 0.01M HCL using a mixture of methyl-red and methyl-blue indicator. The analysis was carried out on triplicate samples. A blank sample titration was also carried out. The volatile bases contained in the receiver solution were determined as given below.

Calculation:

$$TVB - N \left(\frac{mg}{100g} \text{ sample} \right) = \frac{(v_1 - v_0) \times 0.14 \times 2 \times 100}{M}$$

(2)

Where:

V_1 = Titre value of 0.01 M HCL solution for the sample

V_0 = Titre value of 0.01 M HCL solution for blank

M = Weight (g) of sample.

pH Determination

The method described by Adeyemi *et al.* (2013) was used for the pH determination. Ten grams of each of the fish sample was homogenized in 50 ml distilled water and the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper No.1. The pH of the filtrate was measured using the pH meter (Jenway pH/Conductivity meter, Model 3540) after calibration with standard buffers of pH 7 and 4 at 25 °C.

Mineral elements analysis

The 36 samples were subjected to elemental analysis using ARL.QUANT'X. EDXRF Analyzer,

Serial Number: 9952120 (Thermo Fisher Scientific Company Switzerland), using the standard method (SRM 2710) for biological samples and IAEA-155 Whey Powder was used as standard reference material. Two grams of each finely ground sample were placed in a sample holder and covered with cotton wool to prevent it from spraying. The sample was inserted into the XRF Spectrometer for the elemental analysis. The samples were allowed to run in the XRF spectrometer for 10 mins, after which the results were obtained.

Statistical Analysis

With the use of SPSS version 25, Inc., USA, data obtained from the laboratory analysis were subjected to Analysis of Variance and a significant test for differences between sample means using Duncan's Multiple.

RESULTS OF THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The result of the PV of the samples is presented in Fig2. Peroxide values recorded were from 4.62±0.03 - 32.97±0.05 mEq O₂/kg in *G. niloticus*, 2.79±0.01 - 34.83±0.05 mEq O₂/kg in *R. sacertodum*, 0.8±0.01-8.82±0.02 mEq O₂/kg in *C. gariepinus* and 6.06±0.06-18.78±0.11 mEq O₂/kg in *E. fimbriata* (Fig2). The wide range of PV observed in each fish species from the different locations was found to be significantly different (P<0.05). An indication of different exposures to factors responsible for the fish deterioration. The highest peroxide values were recorded from the ING location in *G. niloticus* (32.97±0.05 mEq O₂/kg and from IWF in *R. sacertodum* (34.83±0.05 mEq O₂/kg) markets. The detection of peroxides in unsaturated fats

and oils serve as the initial indicator of rancidity. The extent of unsaturation in fats and oils plays a very important role in driving the process of autoxidation. The susceptibility of the oil to rancidity is heightened by the degree of unsaturation, which ultimately leads to the formation of off-flavours (Shahidi and Hossain, 2022). The variation in PV may be due to the processing method, as each fish sample was handled and processed by different processors

from different locations, and the applied temperature also varied considerably. While peroxide was indeed detected in the four fish species across all market locations, it is important to note that the PV of most of the samples were within the maximum acceptable value of 15 mEq O₂/Kg of oil as recommended by the Codex Alimentarius commission (Codex Alimentarius, 1999). Only a few of the samples exceeded this limit

Fig. 2 The pH of smoke-dried fish samples sourced from different retail open markets within Imo State (Fig2). The values obtained from *R. sacertodum* (34.83 mEq O₂/kg) and *G. niloticus* (32.97 mEq O₂/kg) both from ING market were found to be twice in excess of the permitted limit of CODEX,

in some locations, the values were considerably low *G. niloticus* from IWD market (4.62±0.03 mEq O₂/kg), *R. sacertodum* from IEA and IEC markets (2.79±0.01 and 2.83±0.05 mEq O₂/kg respectively). These values were also significantly different at P<0.05. Thus, suggesting that the smoke-dried fish lacked

regulation and control. The exceeded limits in the fish samples may be attributed to the factors that Nowsad et al. (2021) mentioned. This author reported that lipid oxidation in fish is influenced by variables such as the initial lipid content in the fish sample, storage temperature, and duration of storage.

Total volatile base nitrogen (TVBN) is used to determine the extent of fish spoilage (Castro *et.al*, 2012). It measures the basic components released during the proteolytic action of bacteria on the nitrogenous compounds contained in the fish (Fig3). This study recorded 7.29 -10.36 mg/kg for *G. niloticus*, 7.81-10.15 mg/kg for *R. sacertodum*, 5.75-10.40 mg/kg for *C. gariepinus*, while *E. fimbriata* was 7.44-10.56 mg/kg. The primary components of TVB-N include trimethylamine, dimethylamine, and ammonia, which increased over the storage period (Jinadasa, 2014). While trimethylamine is

a product of bacterial decomposition, ammonia is the breakdown of amino acids, which consequently contributes to a reduction in the quality of the fish. Conversely, as storage time increases, an elevation in TVB-N levels suggests a decline in quality and is an effective indicator of the advanced stages of spoilage. Specifically, fresh fish typically contains a TVB-N content ranging from 35 to 40 mg/kg of fish with variations depending on the fish species (Nowsad *et al.* 2021). The TVB-N values obtained in the present study were found to be below the established rejection limit for TVBN quality standards, and this could be due to non-degradation of the fish protein (Nowsad *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the effect of the smoke on the bacterial content of the fish may have contributed to the reduction of the bacteria, causing the degradation of the protein, resulting in low values for TVBN reported.

Fig. 3 Total volatile base nitrogen (TVBN) of smoke-dried fish samples sourced from different retail open markets within Imo State

The pH value is acknowledged as a factor that affects the physicochemical, microbiological and sensory quality aspects of the processed fish. pH is a crucial parameter in establishing a product's quality, because a decline in the quality of fresh fish might have an impact on the pH content (Susanto et al., 2011). Even though the samples of the fish species had different numerical pH values as shown in Table 1, the results generally stayed within the neutral pH range of 7, with some variations slightly above but below 8. The result of the pH of the samples is presented in Fig4. Values obtained ranged from 7.65 ± 0.02 in *G. niloticus* (location INI) to 7.99 ± 0.02 for *C. gariepinus* (location IEC). The pH value of fresh fish is 6.8, as deterioration begins, the spoilage bacteria are responsible for the breakdown of the nitrogenous compounds. Proteolysis products are usually basic, and this includes ammonia and

trimethylamine (Swastawati et al., 2022; Simeonidou et al., 1997; Tnuwo et al., 2019). These products caused an increase in pH. Hence, the pH may act as an indicator of the quality of the product (Susanto et al., 2011). Almost all the samples showed a pH above 7.0. *C. gariepinus* and *G. niloticus* gave the highest pH value in all the locations examined. *E. fimbriata* has the lowest pH between 7 and 7.5. This may be attributed to the difference in the content of nitrogenous substances, harvesting techniques, biological state, the smoking techniques and extent of exposure to bacterial contaminants (Howgate 2009; Ozogul 2010). Thus, an increase in pH may be caused by spoilage bacteria, producing proteolytic enzymes. Since the ideal pH range for typical fish products is between 6.0 and 8.0, the pH values in this study are considered appropriate for smoked fish products (Abbas et al., 2008). The location did not affect the variation in the pH.

Fig. 4 The pH values of smoke-dried fish samples sourced from different retail open markets within Imo State

MINERAL ELEMENT CONTENT OF SMOKE-DRIED FISH SAMPLES

The result of the mineral elements of biological importance of the fish samples, which include As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn, are presented in Table 2 with a standard reference in Table 3. The analyzed minerals in this work are vital to assess the nutritional quality, establish the fish's safety, and meet the regulatory standards of the smoked fish samples sold in Imo State.

Trace elements like iron (Fe), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mg), chromium (Cr), which are generally required by the body in smaller amounts for various physiological functions, were confirmed to be present. Arsenic (As) and Lead (Pb) were not detected in all the fish species, across all sample locations, indicating the fish samples were free from these

metals' (As and Pb) toxicity. Lall and Kaushik (2021) stated that fish have unique physiological mechanisms, similar to other vertebrates, enabling them to absorb minerals from their diet and the surrounding water. Other researchers have confirmed the presence of these mineral elements such as Al, Cr, Ni, Ca, Mg, Na, K, Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn, As, Fe, Mn, Hg in fish samples (Emurotu *et al.*, 2014; Bozena *et al.*, 2019; Adeosun *et al.*, 2020). While some of these mineral elements are essential nutrients, the presence of elements like Pb has no specific biological function and is toxic even in trace amounts (Adeosun *et al.*, 2020). In addition, these essential elements (Fe, Cu, Mn, and Zn) with established biological functions are potentially toxic when the human body is exposed to excessive concentrations. Many of these metal elements have been found to be carcinogenic and can lead to severe health issues, including liver disorders, cardiovascular

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difficulties, kidney dysfunctions, and, in extreme cases, death (Taslina *et al.* 2022).

The recommended permissible limit for chromium (Cr) ranged from 0.15 - 1 ppm, as indicated in Table 3. The concentration of chromium from this study ranged from 0.00 - 1.63 ppm for *R. sacertodum*, 0.00 - 1.15 ppm for *G. niloticus*, 0.00 - 4.34 ppm for *C. gariepinus* and 0.00 - 4.07 ppm for *E. fimbriata*. Cr is an essential metal necessary for the metabolism of carbohydrates and improves insulin activity in the body. However, it is important to note that Cr and its compounds are well-known toxins if ingested more than the recommended limits. Cr comes in a variety of forms, some of which are dangerous, such as hexavalent chromium (Cr (VI)). Chromium in food can cause diarrhoea, vomiting, stomach distress, bone fractures, mutagenic and carcinogenic effects, infertility and teratogenicity, and damage to the neurological and immunological systems (Ali *et al.*, 2014). Chromium can be found in woods that are used to smoke fish, and if the wood contains chromium, it may be deposited on the fish during the smoking process. There is a high risk of contamination if smoked fish comes into contact with chromium-containing materials or surroundings, particularly under certain storage circumstances. Chromium concentration that was above the current study has been reported (Oguzie and Izevbogie, 2009).

The permissible limit of Fe, as shown in Table 3, is 100 ppm. The Fe present in the current study showed that *G. niloticus* ranged from 66.48 - 188.1 ppm, *R. sacertodum* ranged from 58.55 - 94.68 ppm, *C. gariepinus* ranged from 62.2 -

204.4 ppm and *E. fimbriata* ranged from 65.06 - 264.8 ppm. *R. sacertodum* samples from all locations were below the permissible limit. However, *E. fimbriata* samples from these market locations exceeded the permissible limit, except samples from IWE and INI (65.06 ppm and 74.3 ppm, respectively) markets. Similarly, samples from four of the markets (IEC, IWD, IWE and IWF) were within the permissible limit of 100 ppm for the *C. gariepinus*. Variation in the concentrations of this element could be attributed to the concentration of Fe in the water body, irrespective of the location and the capacity of the fish to absorb and convert this essential metal from their diet or the surrounding water (Emurotu *et al.*, 2014).

Copper plays important roles in metabolism and haemoglobin synthesis as a key component of essential enzymes, nevertheless, excessive copper intake, particularly from seafood with high concentrations, poses significant health risks, potentially leading to kidney and liver damage (Aljabryn, 2022). In this study, the concentration of copper (Cu) (Table 3) was found to be within the permissible limits of 30 ppm, except for specific samples, *E. fimbriata* from ING market (35.4ppm), *G. niloticus* from INH (35.02ppm), IEC (44.9ppm) markets, and *R. sacertodum* from INI market (108.66ppm). For *C. gariepinus*, the Cu concentration ranged from 2.33 to 41.66 ppm, exceeding the permissible limit only in the IWE market sample, with 41.66 ppm Cu.

Table 2: Important mineral elements of fish species sourced from different retail market locations within Imo State

Element	Fish species	Sample location/Concentration (ppm)								
		IEA	IEB	IEC	IWD	IWE	IWF	ING	INH	INI
As	<i>G. niloticus</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cr	<i>G. niloticus</i>	1.15	0.95	0.7	0.19	2	0.65	0	0.33	0
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	0.98	1.63	0	0.19	0	0.58	1.1	1.26	0.7
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	0.44	0	0.55	1.69	2.92	0.5	2.02	0.51	4.34
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	4.07	2.04	2.5	0.55	0	1.14	1.26	2.95	0.46
Cu	<i>G. niloticus</i>	13.81	16.88	2.7	1.03	9.37	1.81	2.46	35.02	8.34
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	1.85	2.59	44.9	2.81	5.05	9.27	2.38	10.01	108.66
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	3.21	5.25	3.41	2.33	41.66	20.93	7.7	9.78	7.6
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	3.83	23.08	1.99	3.08	2.82	4.55	35.4	16.85	2.27
Fe	<i>G. niloticus</i>	66.48	100.01	167	68.09	188.1	108.82	70.04	87.93	78.47
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	59.21	64.19	70.79	58.55	65.94	73.03	74.89	71.47	94.68

	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	103.8	204.4	62.2	83.24	95.96	90.85	117.77	115.89	173.2
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	145.7	109.23	102.9	237.4	65.06	264.8	148	102.74	74.3
Mn	<i>G. niloticus</i>	2.53	4.89	11.31	4.72	6.62	7.43	5.19	6.48	4.05
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	3.54	3.79	4.47	3.84	4.45	6.64	6.59	4.17	4.38
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	7.91	23.61	3.72	5.54	5.46	4.73	4.74	4.39	9.89
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	13.18	10.44	9.83	14.83	8.49	12.04	10.09	8.44	8.04
Ni	<i>G. niloticus</i>	10.8	21.3	18.9	14.7	22.4	17.1	13.9	12.8	21.1
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	17	18.6	9	14	29.3	17.3	16.8	26.8	29.5
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	25	15.2	17.5	21.5	14.8	52.3	18.4	31.8	24.7
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	6.6	2.3	12.6	8.5	7.8	23.3	19.5	13.8	10
Pb	<i>G. niloticus</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Zn	<i>G. niloticus</i>	54.37	67.37	44.93	50.53	84.45	50.58	62.01	84.79	64.09
	<i>R. sacertodum</i>	50.44	57	51.27	63.98	54.31	64.25	56.53	50.41	80.22
	<i>C. gariepinus</i>	64.2	67.95	61.57	47.72	54.5	111.82	56.41	51.96	72.49
	<i>E. fimbriata</i>	45.63	35.04	42.16	42.31	41.27	37.21	48.1	35.5	45.61

ND – Not detected

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Table 3: The maximum concentrations of metal elements of biological importance detected in the present study and maximum permissible levels for fish muscle tissues

	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Source
Maximum value detected in <i>G. niloticus</i> (ppm)	N 2	2	35.02	188.1	11.31	22.4	ND	84.79	This study
Maximum value detected in <i>R. sacertodum</i> (ppm)	N 1.63	1.63	108.66	94.68	6.64	29.5	ND	80.22	This study
Maximum value detected in <i>E. fimbriata</i> (ppm)	N 4.07	4.07	35.4	264.8	14.83	23.3	ND	48.1	This study
Maximum value detected in <i>C. gariepinus</i> (ppm)	N 4.34	4.34	41.66	204.4	23.61	52.3	ND	111.82	This study
World Health Organization (WHO) (ppm)			30	100	1		2.0	100	Tore <i>et al</i> (2021)
Codex Alimentarius Commission (ppm)							0.3		Tore <i>et al</i> (2021)

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)	1	0.15-1	30	100	1	80	0.5	30-40	Rakib <i>et al.</i> (2021), Ekweozor <i>et al.</i> (2017) Tore <i>et al.</i> (2021), Wangboje and Miller (2018)
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ND – Not detected

Nickel can accumulate in surface water from various sources, such as combustion of fossil fuels, old battery trash, vehicle components, coins, stainless steel and Ni alloys (Ahmad *et al.*, 2009). When there is prolonged exposure of the fish's body to high concentrations, Ni can cause respiratory issues, and it is carcinogenic. The acute toxicity results from competitive interactions with calcium, cobalt, copper, iron, and zinc (Moore *et al.*, 1985). Nickel values ranged from 10.8 – 22.4 ppm for *G. niloticus*, 9 – 29.3 ppm for *R. sacertodum*, 14.8 – 52.3 for *C. gariepinus* and 2.3 – 23.3ppm for *E. fimbriata* (Table 2). The concentration varied across the sample locations; however, values fall within the permissible limit of 80 ppm as recommended in Table 3. Differences in the nickel concentrations may arise from the source where the fish was harvested before smoking, handling practices, as well as environmental conditions (Aljabryn, 2022).

Zinc is an essential trace element for human metabolism and nutrition. It plays a vital role in numerous biochemical processes (Kelle *et al.*, 2018). Nevertheless, the consumption of

excessive amounts of zinc may produce toxic effects characterized by symptoms of irritability, muscular stiffness and pain (Abukakar *et al.*, 2023). The Zn content across all fish species ranged from 44.93 – 84.79 ppm for *G. niloticus*, 50.41 – 80.22 ppm for *R. sacertodum*, 47.72 – 111.82 ppm for *C. gariepinus* and 35.04 – 48.1 ppm for *E. fimbriata* samples. Values across fish species in all market locations exceeded the permissible limit recommended by FAO (Ekweozor *et al.*, 2017; Wangboje and Miller, 2018; Rakib *et al.*, 2021; Tore *et al.*, 2021) but were within the permissible limit of 100 ppm recommended by WHO (Tore *et al.*, 2021). The implication of this is that the fish samples do not pose an immediate chemical hazard to people consuming the fish found in these markets, except the *C. gariepinus* sample from the IWF market with the highest value of 111.82 ppm.

Manganese (Mn) is essential in trace amounts as it plays a role in regulating cellular energy, bone and connective tissue growth, as well as blood clotting, however, excessive exposure to high levels of manganese can lead to health concerns such as neurological effects (Authur *et al.*, 2021). The concentration of Mn ranged from 2.53- 11.31

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ppm for *G. niloticus*, 3.54- 6.54 ppm for *R. sacertodum*, 8.04 – 14.83 ppm for *E. fimbriata*, while that of *C. gariepinus* samples ranged from 3.72 – 23.61 ppm. These values for the fish species across different market locations were above the recommended limits by FAO and WHO (2021), as referenced in Table 3. On the contrary, Tore *et al.* (2023) recorded a concentration of 10.29 ppm of Mn in fish, which is above the permissible limit for fish.

CONCLUSION

Generally, the fish market location has not played any significant role in the parameters considered in this study, PV, TVBN, pH and elemental composition. Suggesting that safety issues relating to the safety of the smoke-dried fish can be controlled, irrespective of its source or location. TVBN concentrations, which serve as an indicator of freshness, were generally within the acceptable limit for all fish samples. These values remained consistently below the predetermined TVBN quality standard rejection limit, confirming that the fish protein retained its optimal quality. Judging by the joint FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission (2021) standard, with an acceptable PV limit set at 15 mEq O₂/Kg, this study shows high PV in some

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fish samples, while some fall within the permissible limit. The absence of toxic elements such as As and Pb makes the fish samples safe for consumption. Certain essential micro-minerals (Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Cr) that could be toxic at higher concentrations exceeded the stipulated guidelines in certain locations. An increase in the frequency of fish consumption or the metal contamination within this area may lead to chronic health effects in the population. It is important to note that in this study, heavy metals such as As, Hg and Pb are not threats in the smoke-dried fish processed for human consumption. The findings show some relatively good alignment with the international standards. However, the main risk issues are the handling and storage practices. None of the fish purchased was packaged and labelled as may be required by best practices and protection from environmental contamination. Old batches could not be differentiated from the new batch; hence, no best-before date could be imposed. Policymakers should consider establishing sustainable national safety standards for smoke-drying that can be implemented and effectively managed by fish processors and handlers.

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